
THE GERMLINE AND THE EPIGENOME: AN ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF GENETIC VARIANTS ON THE EPIGENETIC LANDSCAPE FOR CANCER STUDY

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ABSTRACT

We present here an overview of the relationship between genomic variants and epigenetic landscape. The strong links between epigenetic alterations and cancer offer interesting targets for the treatment of cancer; however, more profound understanding of the biological processes involved is necessary to translate these opportunities into clinical practice. Systematic analysis of the use of machine learning models with genetic and epigenetic variants is also crucial to robustly leverage recent advances in computational methods. To this end, we describe some of the problematics involved through a case study on the ENTE_x dataset.

Keywords Germline variants · Epigenetics · Cancer

1 The role of epigenetics in biological processes

The growth, function, and maintenance of cells is mediated primarily by proteins, chains of amino acids that perform an astounding variety of processes through their structural properties. The information necessary to produce proteins is transcribed and translated from the DNA, which ultimately acts as a central repository of information for the cell. Selective expression of genes and modification of the resulting proteins are crucial for healthy development of organisms and, when disrupted, provide causes and progression factors for disease states.

Several control mechanisms acting primarily to regulate transcription fall within the label of *epigenetic mechanisms*. Transcription of genes can be controlled by altering the chemical properties of the DNA molecule to inhibit or promoting the binding of proteins to the nucleotide chain. Such is the case for DNA Methylation, the addition of a methyl group to the 5'-position of cytosine residues, which is involved primarily in gene inhibition [1, 2], or the chemical modification of the histone molecules around which the DNA is wrapped to form chromatin [3].

Alternatively, the accessibility of genes can be regulated by altering the chromatin state, i.e. controlling how tightly the complex structure composed of DNA and histones is packed. This state can be changed by histone modifications [4], by altering the spacing of nucleosomes with chromatin remodelling complexes [5], or by non-coding RNA [6]. In addition to controlling gene access at the transcriptional level by regulating chromatin state, RNA-mediated control mechanisms can act at the translational and post-translational steps by controlling RNA degradation and silencing [7].

2 The epigenetics of cancer

Epigenetic mechanisms are crucial for developing and maintaining the expression levels of the genes that characterize each cell type. A growing number of studies has revealed the role that mutations in the epigenetic machinery as well as the cell-type specific epigenomes play in human disease [8, 9, 10]. Germline variants in the DNA sequence that affect epigenetic regulators can have system-wide effect on the establishment or interpretation of epigenetic marks. Additionally, inherited genomic sequence variants can cause local variations in epigenomic patterns across cell-types

[11]. Also, somatic epigenomic variations may be introduced through cellular integration of external signals with genetic factors.

Disruptions in the epigenetic landscape can result in altered gene expression or function, and potentially lead to carcinogenesis. Global changes in the epigenome are strongly linked to the hallmarks of cancer [12], and provide both useful biomarkers [13, 14] and potential therapeutic targets [15]. Genome-wide alterations of DNA methylation are common in many cancers [16]; furthermore, these disruptions play a causal role in tumour growth by silencing tumour suppressors [17, 18], activating oncogenes [19], and regulating metastasis [20].

Within the framework of precision medicine, epigenetic mutations are currently studied mainly for their potential in early detection and drug response prediction [21, 22, 23]. However, recent advances in epigenome editing methods [24] offer exciting opportunities for direct interventions on the epigenome for the treatment of cancer [25], which could be particularly promising when paired with cancer immunotherapy [26].

3 Effects of germline variants and somatic mutations on the epigenome

Within the analysis of cancer specifically, germline genetic variants that affect the epigenetic landscape are of particular interest [27]. Germline mutations can affect the epigenome by either disrupting the general patterns of epigenetic modifications, or by affecting the regions of the DNA that encode epigenetic controllers.

The first category includes single nucleotide polymorphisms and the motifs that emerge from the altered sequence, which can lead to cancer susceptibility by altering DNA methylation and patterns of histone modifications [28, 29].

Alterations in epigenetic regulatory enzymes have been shown to correlate with tumour onset and progression [30]. This link is particularly strong for mutations in the DNA methyltransferase (DNMT) family [31], with mutations in DNMT1 and DNMT3A described in leukaemias, prostate, and colorectal cancers [32, 33, 34].

The enzymes controlling histone methylation and acetylation are also important factors in several cancers. Histone methylation is involved in crucial processes including DNA repair, gene expression, cell differentiation and replication [35]. Mutations in histone methyltransferases (HMTs) feature prominently in several types of lymphoma [36, 37], while histone acetyltransferases (HATs) and histone deacetylases (HDACs) are associated with tumour progression [38]. Inhibitors targeting mutations in these enzymes are showing promise for cancer treatment, either by directly acting on the affected biological process or through synthetic lethality [39]. Mutations in the proteins composing chromatin remodelling complexes are some of the most widespread among human cancers and are, therefore, the target of considerable interest for the development of novel therapies [40, 41, 42].

Mutations of the regions encoding epigenetic regulators can be acquired somatically, but they also constitute a risk when inherited through the germline, as they can become cancer genes following a loss of wild-type allele event [43].

4 Challenges in the analysis of interactions between somatic and germline variants and observed phenotypes

Machine learning models provide exciting opportunities for applications to genetic variants and the epigenome. Numerous work in the literature achieved astonishing results within this scope for pattern recognition, identification of biomarkers, phenotype prediction and more [44, 45]. Particularly appealing is the enormous amount of data generated by sequencing experiments in high-throughput setups, which enables the use of powerful yet demanding approaches such as deep learning. However, sequencing data and biological data more generally pose considerable challenges that must be addressed to improve our understanding of the biological processes analysed, ranging from noisy data, distributional shifts, confounding, and more [46].

Here, we highlight a different problematic that arises when analysing the interactions between germline and somatic variants, and observed phenotypes. Within this framework, the causal process that determines the phenotype is crucial in determining what an algorithm can and cannot learn. We present here a small case study to offer a practical example of the challenges posed by the influence of germline and somatic variants.

In this case study, we consider the task of imputing unobserved epigenomic measurements using as input data a selection of observed epigenomic experiments. This imputation setting, which has been analysed in several works in the literature [47, 48] provides an interesting test bed to examine how machine learning models learn from sequencing data.

We selected 116 ChIP-seq tracks from the ENTEEx dataset, a collaboration between the ENCODE [49, 50] and the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) consortia created new data sets that include extensive individual-specific histone modification measurements from four cadaveric donors, as well as called variants. The individuals are labelled using

Figure 1: An 800,000-Bp span of chromosome 21 for the H3K4me3 assay in sigmoid colon samples. The peaks of signals are to a large extent shared between individuals.

their sex and recorded age (i.e. 37 y.o. male, 54 y.o. male, 53 y.o. female, and 51 y.o. female). Following previous works in the literature, we used the $-\log_{10}(p - value)$ signals binned to a resolution of 25 bp, and applied an \arcsinh transform.

We chose chromosome 21 as a representative region of the genome, and trained an eDICE model [51] to predict held-out epigenomic tracks for a target individual, using the same hyperparameters described in the paper. The model was first trained for 20 epochs with a learning rate of 10^{-4} on the three remaining individual, before being fine-tuned on a subset of the tracks available for the target for 5 epochs with a learning rate of 10^{-5} , to then predict the remaining target data.

This imputation task is challenging for several reasons. Firstly, a large portion of the enrichment patterns are shared between individuals (example in Figure 1); however, what we are most interested in predicting are the individual-specific enrichment pattern that differentiate each individual from the rest.

Algorithms such as eDICE can learn to infer these specific patterns under certain conditions. When the cause of individual-specific enrichment falls among the mechanisms of epigenetic inheritance previously described, it is plausible that a good machine learning algorithm can learn the relevant correlation with the observed data. Such is the case of germline single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) variants, which can affect histone modifications [29]. In Figure 2 we visualized a region with peaks of enrichment present for the individual labelled "Male 37", but not the remaining three individuals. This enrichment region appears in most of the tissues gathered from "Male 37"; this observation, paired with the presence of called variants in the genetic sequence, leads us to conclude that this is likely an alteration caused by inheritance. As we can observe, eDICE manages to predict the presence of this enrichment quite well.

On the other hand, if the cause of changes in the epigenomic pattern is somatic, i.e. derived from an acquired mutation or a specific kind of environmental exposure and interaction, then it will likely be found only in one tissue for one individual. The occupancy histograms in Figures 3a and 3b display the occupancy of each enriched bin in chromosome 21, i.e. across how many tissues and individuals each of these enrichments are shared.

We can observe that epigenomic pattern sharing change significantly based on the assay performed. For some histone modifications, such as H3K9me3, there is a considerable portion of enriched regions that are not shared across tissues nor individuals. In this case, none of the observed samples directly contains the relevant information necessary for inference, and we do not expect the model to easily pick up on this signal.

Therefore, we hypothesize that to properly capture the effect of somatic variants in the analysis of a given phenotype, it would be valuable to have multiple sources of information related to the sample being analysed, such as different data views or modalities. On the other hand, phenotypes due to inherited factors such as germline variants have the potential to be captured by a machine learning model when the input data includes several measurements affected by the same inherited changes.

Figure 2: On the left, a plot of an altered pattern of enrichment for the histone modification H3K4me3 in one individual (37 years old male adult) but not the others. The same genomic position is displayed on the right for several tissues for the target individual. The two peaks in the middle occur together with several inherited variants; as they are shared across most tissues, this individual-specific enrichment pattern represents most likely an example of epigenetic alteration inherited through the germline.

5 Conclusion

We have presented an analysis of some challenges involved in the analysis of interactions between somatic and germline variants, and observed phenotypes. We chose here epigenomic modifications as phenotypic information, due to the crucial role they play in healthy development and human disease. Of particular interest are the opportunities that a more profound understanding of epigenetics can offer for cancer treatment, due to the extensive associations between epigenetic factors and several types of cancer. We reviewed the mechanisms through which acquired and inherited factors influence the epigenome, and presented a case study to highlight the challenges that the use of machine learning models poses in this setting. Specifically, we selected the task of epigenomic imputation as the test bed using the ENTE_x dataset, and highlighted the different aspects involved in the prediction task. Inherited factors shared across samples offer a shared source of signal that can be picked up by the eDICE model we trained, allowing for the prediction of individual-specific enrichment patterns. Acquired mutations in the genome and epigenome, that do not propagate systemically, are likely not shared across tissues nor individuals; therefore, we do not expect a model such as eDICE to be able to predict this tissue- and individual-specific enrichment.

We emphasize that the role played by germline and somatic variants in the analysis of a phenotype must be considered in the design of the model and the selection of the data to analyse to obtain robust results from machine learning models.

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The germline and the epigenome

Figure 3: Occupancy histograms for two selected histone modifications (H3K4me3 and H3K9me3) across tissues and individuals.

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Data accessibility

The epigenomic tracks for the 4 individuals part of the ENTEEx dataset can be found on the portal for the ENCODE project <https://www.encodeproject.org/>. The called variants for the individual Male 37 have accession code ENCFF233IAO. The accession codes for the 116 ChIP-seq experiments from the ENTEEx dataset are found in Table 1. The assembly mismatch between the measurements and the called variants was resolved using NCBI Remap¹.

Tissue	Assay	ENCDO845WKR (male 37 years old)	ENCDO451RUA (male 54 years old)	ENCDO793LXB (female 53 years old)	ENCDO271OUW (female 51 years old)
ascending aorta	H3K27ac			ENCFF472VCY	ENCFF002VCM
	H3K36me3			ENCFF529EEQ	ENCFF602IDJ
	H3K4me1			ENCFF971TZV	ENCFF843GKY
	H3K4me3			ENCFF229NZH	ENCFF383JQU
	H3K9me3			ENCFF616UAG	ENCFF644UVB
thoracic aorta	H3K27ac	ENCFF652JBU	ENCFF344YDV		
	H3K36me3	ENCFF700ZLW	ENCFF556REM		
	H3K4me1	ENCFF141KEC	ENCFF388BWY		s
	H3K4me3	ENCFF327VEH	ENCFF723SJI		
	H3K9me3	ENCFF221YER	ENCFF198OYC		
esophagus muscularis mucosa	H3K27ac	ENCFF969PNR	ENCFF437XOA	ENCFF282WYM	ENCFF707HDC
	H3K36me3	ENCFF476ILL	ENCFF567TNH	ENCFF723KNC	ENCFF861YVB
	H3K4me1	ENCFF295FVH	ENCFF478GEN	ENCFF067DEH	ENCFF877IZN
	H3K4me3	ENCFF280VIW	ENCFF979ERR	ENCFF156BAJ	ENCFF636QVZ
	H3K9me3	ENCFF501FLV	ENCFF380LRK	ENCFF885KSL	ENCFF729RCC
stomach	H3K27ac	ENCFF440VXQ	ENCFF241NFR	ENCFF134NHD	ENCFF140JKH
	H3K36me3	ENCFF302OSD	ENCFF414FQR	ENCFF428LSW	ENCFF441GAP
	H3K4me1	ENCFF140RPG	ENCFF034VHX	ENCFF411ZSD	ENCFF131UFO
	H3K4me3	ENCFF175WCH	ENCFF221JKN	ENCFF309DCR	ENCFF468UJW
	H3K9me3	ENCFF285GPE	ENCFF765FRJ	ENCFF674DMF	ENCFF554RBC
upper lobe of left lung	H3K27ac	ENCFF204PWD	ENCFF305XCG	ENCFF071QUR	ENCFF178DCM
	H3K36me3	ENCFF549PDA	ENCFF572VAG	ENCFF267DPL	ENCFF700BQU
	H3K4me1	ENCFF076BNQ	ENCFF614CUN	ENCFF777AOP	ENCFF344GZI
	H3K4me3	ENCFF898DYH	ENCFF526RLU	ENCFF887IUV	ENCFF5780BF
	H3K9me3	ENCFF672QOH	ENCFF583KBZ	ENCFF076RRH	ENCFF317KCA
sigmoid colon	H3K27ac	ENCFF669TSI	ENCFF507VUO	ENCFF156QWL	ENCFF497GAF
	H3K36me3	ENCFF284VTI	ENCFF312AHC	ENCFF577WWK	ENCFF744WIO
	H3K4me1	ENCFF686SIG	ENCFF427WMO	ENCFF1261MK	ENCFF113YOI
	H3K4me3	ENCFF892GNP	ENCFF445QHF	ENCFF905JEN	ENCFF135XHH
	H3K9me3	ENCFF811EKT	ENCFF925APW	ENCFF782WTP	ENCFF477NHW
spleen	H3K27ac	ENCFF230ZQJ	ENCFF786NLG	ENCFF735GSH	ENCFF702AJP
	H3K4me1	ENCFF873LAX	ENCFF049HBP	ENCFF402YZU	ENCFF599IBO
	H3K4me3	ENCFF422ZXF	ENCFF189KXE	ENCFF656AAS	ENCFF462VQE
	H3K9me3	ENCFF952NOQ	ENCFF418KYC	ENCFF447CEL	ENCFF088KFT

Table 1: Accession codes for the 116 selected tracks from the ENTEEx dataset.

¹<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/tools/remap>